

Benefits of Cochlear Implant in Children: The Parents Perspective

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Abstract

Background and Objective: The language is the medium by which communicate and sound is the power source to understand the language these are our years and the hearing sense contact as with the word. The objective of this study is to analysis the subjective benefits of cochlear implantation in children according to parents' Perspective.

Method: It was carried out in children aged 2-3 years. A self-designed questionnaire was used to assess the potential point of view. The questionnaires were filled by parents included the following sections: hearing, communication and psychosocial.

Results: The findings of the current study indicate that cochlear implants positively impact the quality of life for both children and their families in various ways. All things related to children had improvement in quality of life after cochlear implant activation. Parents were more satisfied with the domains communication, self-reliance and social relations because it affects more on child's life.

Conclusion: The ability to hear enabled the children to integrate into the hearing community and develop spoken language skills. Parents observed that cochlear implants significantly enhanced their children's quality of life, particularly in boosting self-esteem, improving social interactions, and facilitating communication.

Keywords: Hearing impairment, Hearing loss, Cochlear implant, Communication, Psychosocial.

INTRODUCTION

Hearing loss is the world's most prevalent disability. Among children, 3 to 4% suffer from profound hearing loss. The introduction of cochlear implants has been a groundbreaking development in audiology. The advent of cochlear implants (CIs) has transformed this, enabling many individuals with CIs to communicate effortlessly, even using cell phones. The progression in CI technology has been rapid and impactful.

Alessandro Volta, primitive experiment involved connecting a battery to metal probes inserted into his ear canals, leading to auditory sensations when the current flowed.

Widespread infant hearing screening has significantly improved the identification of hearing loss in newborns worldwide. Evidence strongly supports the benefits of early implantation in children. Studies have shown that children receiving implants between 12 and 36 months perform better than those implanted later, between 37 and 60 months. This finding, along with earlier detection of hearing loss in children, has led to a decrease in the age of implantation. Initially, cochlear implants

were not recommended for children under 2 years old, but this has changed with advancements in technology and clinical trials, such as those with the Nucleus 22 and Clarion devices. Today, cochlear implants are deemed safe for children as young as 12 months, and the FDA has approved implants for this age group since 2000.

However, implanting CIs in children younger than 12 months remains a subject of debate. The primary limitation is the challenge of accurately assessing severe to profound sensorineural hearing loss in very young children. Generally, with modern techniques, a reliable diagnosis can be made by the time a child is 12 months old, with earlier assessments possible in cases of hereditary hearing loss or meningitis.

The pediatric cochlear implant program was started in 1994 at St. Augustinus Hospital in 1994. The implantation was given to children younger than 2 years of age and in 2000 it was given to children younger than 1 year of age. For profoundly deaf children a steadily decreasing age and early clinical interventions were used for cochlear implantation.⁵ Although it is widely accepted that at the time of implantation, age is a significant factor for developing intelligibility and speech perception in pediatric implants. After cochlear implantation many pre-linguistically deaf children have experienced significant improvement in speech production, language skills and speech perception. Currently children are receiving cochlear implantations who are suffering from hearing impairment at a steadily decreasing age.⁶

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research took place in the Audiology Department of Fatima Memorial College of Medicine & Dentistry (IAHS), with data collection occurring at the Audiology Center on Sir Syed Road, Gulberg-III, Lahore. The study, an observational descriptive analysis, was completed within six months following the synopsis approval. It did not involve any treatment interventions. The study focused on approximately 50 subjects who had received cochlear implants, specifically targeting children with severe to profound hearing loss. Data was gathered using a self-designed questionnaire tailored to meet the inclusion criteria of the study.

Firstly, we counsel the parents of hearing-impaired children and a self-designed questionnaire used in data collection. And sure, about the questionnaire that it is valid and reliable in exploring parental views and experiences on outcomes of cochlear implants. The questionnaires comprise 20 statements with different aspects.

This study was a cross-sectional research project, gathering data from Jinnah, General, and UOL teaching hospitals. The study was conducted over a six-month period following the approval of its synopsis, with a sample size of 85. Patient recruitment was executed using a convenience sampling method. Eligibility for the study required participants to have a physician-confirmed hypertension diagnosis, be 20 years or older, and have been attending any of the selected hospitals' clinics for at least six months prior to the study. Patients with cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, neurological conditions, or dementia were excluded.

Age and gender, integral to personal identification, were recorded with high precision. The reliability and accuracy of this data were evident in the 100% successful matching across various registers using the personal identification number.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis will be conducted using SPSS version 23.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). Continuous

variables such as age and weight will be presented as mean and standard deviation, while categorical variables will be expressed in terms of frequency and percentage. Charts will be utilized for data visualization, and analysis will include the calculation of mean, count, and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

1. Descriptive Analysis

The data was collected from parents of 50 hearing impaired children. A self-designed questionnaire was used for data collection and parents answered the questions after effective use of cochlear implant. The children were of age limit 1-6 years. Out of 50 subjects 34 are males and 16 females.

2. Gender of Patients

The gender distribution of hearing-impaired implant children is as, males were 34 out of 50 (68%) and the females are 16 out of 50 (32%).

Table 2. Gender of the patients

Gender	Frequency
Male	34(68%)
Female	16(32%)
Total	50(100%)

Graph 2. Gender of the patients

3. Age of Patients

Patients between age group of 2-4 years.

Table No.3. Descriptive Statistics of Age

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	50	2	4	4.62	1.4234

Develop spoken language in children

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 31(62.0%) agreed with this and 12(24.0%) gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	31	62.0

Neither agree nor disagree	12	24.0
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.1 develop spoken language in children

Effective daily communication

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 18(36.0%) agreed with this, 25(50.0%) gives neutral response and 2(4.0%) disagree with this were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	18	36.0
Neither agree nor disagree	25	50.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.2 effective daily communication

Response on call

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 8(16.0%). Strongly agreed with this, 20(40.0%) agreed with this, 14(28.0%) Neither agree nor disagree, 6(12.0%) disagree with gives and 2(4.0%) strongly disagree response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	8	16.0
Agree	20	40.0
Neither agree nor disagree	14	28.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.3 response on call

Engage with others

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 11(22.0%) strongly agreed with this, 22(44.0%) agreed with this and 11(22.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	22.0
Agree	22	44.0
Neither agree nor disagree	11	22.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.4 engage with others

Major Improvements

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this and 18(36.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	18	36.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0

Table 4.5 major improvements

Speech and language therapy improvements

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 9(18.0%) strongly agreed with this, 27(54.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	9	18.0
Agree	27	54.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.6 speech and language therapy improvements

Way of response on sounds

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 17(34.0%) neither agree nor disagree, 4(8.0%) Disagree with and 2(8.0%) strongly disagree gives were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	17	34.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.7 way of response on sounds

Social isolation

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 10(20.0%) strongly agreed with this, 26(52.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	10	20.0
Agree	26	52.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.8 social isolation

Sociable with friends

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 22(42.0%) agreed with this and 21(42.0%), 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	22	44.0
Neither agree nor disagree	21	42.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.9 sociable with friends

Relation with siblings

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 3(9.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this and 20(40.0%), 6(12.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	3	6.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	20	40.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.10 relation with siblings

Behavior improvement

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 29(58.0%) agreed with this and 13(26.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	29	58.0
Neither agree nor disagree	13	26.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.11 behavior improvement

Aware of things

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 4(8.0%) strongly agreed with this, 30(60.0%) agreed with this and 10(20.0%), 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	4	8.0
Agree	30	60.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.12 aware of things

Amuse with music and listening

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 24(48.0%) agreed with this 11(22.0%) neither agree nor disagree and 6(12.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	24	48.0
Neither agree nor disagree	11	22.0
Disagree	6	12.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.13 amuse with music and listening

Frustration after implant

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 11(22.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this 16(32.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	11	22.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	16	32.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.14 frustration after implant

Daily activities after implant

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 21(42.0%) agreed with this, 19(38.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	21	42.0
Neither agree nor disagree	19	38.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.15 daily activities after implant

Education performance

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 26(52.0%) agreed with this, 14(28.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	26	52.0
Neither agree nor disagree	14	28.0
Disagree	4	8.0

Strongly disagree	0	0.0
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Table 4.16 education performance

Cope with mainstream school

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 7(14.0%) strongly agreed with this, 27(54.0%) agreed with this, 10(20.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	7	14.0
Agree	27	54.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	2	4.0

Table 4.17 cope with mainstream school

Child's participation

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 5(10.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 18(36.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	18	36.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.18 child's participation

4.19 Child education with compare to normal students

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 6(12.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 19(38.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 2(4.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	6	12.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	19	38.0
Disagree	2	4.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.19 child education with compare to normal students

Encourage your child

Out of 50 individuals involved in study, 13(26.0%) strongly agreed with this, 23(46.0%) agreed with this, 10(20.0%) neither agree nor disagree with this and 4(8.0%) disagree gives neutral response were included in this data collection.

Scale	frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	13	26.0
Agree	23	46.0
Neither agree nor disagree	10	20.0
Disagree	4	8.0
Strongly disagree	0	0.0

Table 4.20 encourage your child

Discussion:

The purpose this study is to assess the outcomes of cochlear implant at different ages. To find out these outcomes is necessary to have a focus vision about their mode of subject, this study analysis the subjective benefits of cochlear implantation in children according to their parents Perspectives. In 2013 a study was conducted by Sue M Archbold, et-al is to assess benefit of cochlear implantations according to their Prespective. They had parents of 70 children who become deaf between the ages of 1-6 year and receive cochlear implant. While in present study we identify the hearing-impaired children with severe degree hearing loss after using cochlear implant. In present study we take sample from 50 implanted children and their families all over the age of 2-4 year of parents usually express great satisfaction with the quality of life in the children and the family after 2-3 years of cochlear implantation. The parents of child answer the question after the effective use of cochlear implant. In 2012 a study was conducted by Governs-PJ and et-al, to analysis the young children outcome of cochlear implantation in relation to the age at implantation. In this study total 70 children participated. In present study we collected data from 50 subjects all over the age of 2-4 year after the 2-3 year of cochlear implantation.

Conclusion

The current study reveals that cochlear implantation, followed by habilitation and speech therapy, significantly enhances the quality of life for both the children and their families. The ability to access auditory information allows these children to integrate into the hearing community and acquire speech skills. Parents noted that the cochlear implant notably improved their children's quality of life, particularly in areas of self-confidence, social interactions, and communication abilities. Overall, there was a marked increase in parental satisfaction regarding their children's overall development and performance.

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